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Informatics as a branch in Indian Academics with case of private universities: *emphasizing Biological Information Sciences*

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Abstract

Informatics is an interdisciplinary field of practice and study and treated as an alternative to information technology as well as computing education. Informatics foci have two ways first is computational and another is information oriented. Informatics is useful and applicable to different types of organizations viz. IT organization, universities, research centers, governments department, social places and so on. Informatics is less mathematical and hence much useful in the interaction of people, information, and technologies. Informatics is thus widely used in diverse areas viz. healthcare, hospitalities, transportation, society, commerce, and business etc. Information technology is closely associated with the Informatics but it has higher components of information fundamentals and basics of information management. Though, Information Science is much similar and synonymous with informatics in many contexts. Universities around the world are offering degrees, training and research programs in the informatics and its subfields. India is a leading education hub in the world and has numerous educational institutions. Use of informatics nomenclature in India is still very much limited. Though, some of the universities (mainly private) have started programs in the field. The paper is conceptual in nature and thus theoretical. It provides a detailed account of informatics, its nature, and types emphasizing the availability of the degree/programs in India with reference to private universities. The paper mainly highlighted the bio-informatics and related areas at a large as far as private universities are concerned.

Keywords

Information science, informatics, IT management, information systems, India, private universities, higher Education, B.Tech, MTech, emerging degrees

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Introduction

Information is considered as a vital resource for each and every type of organizations and institutions and there is an emerging need to manage the information in different sectors with various perspectives. Informatics is an applied domain responsible for the affairs of the collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination of information with the tools, technologies, and systems [1,7,12]. Fig. 1 is showing the activities and core agenda of the domain informatics at a glance. India is developing rapidly and here various educational institutions are emerging at different levels. As far as higher educational institutions are concerned universities are rising rapidly and thus among the emerging and new subjects Informatics becomes popular and various branches are started in different academic settings.

Figure 1. Foundation and main dealing of Informatics (Paul, 2016)

Private universities in India are now showing their interest in offering Informatics branch mainly its subfield and also domain centric informatics. The various areas and governance of informatics includes (but not limited to)—

- Informatics related to the social sciences
- Informatics related to the pure sciences
- Informatics related to the bio sciences
- Informatics related to the linguistics and languages etc.

The common and most popular branches of Informatics worldwide include health informatics, bio informatics, geo informatics etc [2, 3, 7]. In India as well these may be treated as most popular branches in higher educational bodies (not only in Private Universities).

Objectives & Methodology

The core aim and objective of this paper is mainly the following (but not limited to the)—

- To know about the basic of informatics including its nature, characteristics, and sub domains in brief.
- To learn about the basic of specific domain based informatics in brief with references to their applicability and uses.
- To know about the university systems in India emphasizing private universities.
- To learn about the educational programs, degrees, concentration & specializations in the field of Informatics emphasizing bio information sciences.
- To learn about the universities started bio Informatics and related field as a branch of study.

As far as the methodologies are concerned, because of case study and policy formulation based work for the present work, review of literature played an important role. Apart from conventional books, journals study the web review also played a great meaning in this study. Most importantly the study of Universities has undertaken with the help of web review conducted 2017. For reaching all the private universities, the UGC URL considered as main link (<https://www.ugc.ac.in/privatuniversity.aspx>). Under this, different universities including private universities have been studied, analyzed and also reported.

Informatics and Informatics as a Branch

Informatics is an applied science and related to information science and computer science. Information activities viz. information collection, selection, organization, management, and dissemination are the core and main fundamentals of informatics. Information processing activities with the technologies are the core philosophy of the domain Informatics. Day by day the sub-branches and sub-domains are increasing in this field. It is important to note that the programs or field Informatics is also called as Information Science [4, 5, 15].

Hence many subjects are available in dual platform viz., health informatics or health information science/ geo informatics or geo information science. Although many academicians believe that health information science (or any other sub-field) rather treated as a domain and field of study whereas health informatics may not be treated as a domain/field. A detail on this concept is provided in Fig. 2.

Hence, informatics when deals with the subject related to pure science that is may be called pure informatics [6, 8, 9]. The followings are a partial list of informatics-

- Computational informatics
- Engineering informatics

Figure 2. Information Science Vis-à-vis Informatics- similarities and dissimilarities (Paul, 2016)

- Environmental informatics
- Irrigation informatics
- Materials informatics
- Evolutionary informatics
- Forest informatics
- Geo informatics
- Hydro informatics.

Bio Information Sciences: A Foundation

Bio information sciences may be considered as a branch of Informatics with the concentration of Bio sciences and allied areas [6, 11, 16]. Among these few important are-

- Bio informatics
- Health informatics
- Nero informatics
- Dental informatics
- Nursing informatics
- Environmental informatics
- Forest informatics
- Geo informatics etc.

In India, among the informatics branches, few popular are bio informatics and geo informatics. Though, in recent past health informatics gained popularity in the Private Universities. Among the bio information science areas most popular in India are bio informatics, and health informatics [10, 13, 17]. However, the IIITM Kerala has started another bio focused informatics called eco informatics with MPhil award. Importantly, as far as this study is concerned this program of IIITM Kerala not considered due to its non-private university status.

Indian Higher Education and Private Universities

India is one of the biggest educational hubs in the world with a huge number of institutions for catering a large number of students community. In India higher education sector is classified into Universities, Institutions of National Importance, Research Centers etc. [14, 18, 22].

Table 1. Private Universities in India (www.ugc.ac.in)

Serial No.	States	No. of Universities
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7
2	Assam	5
3	Bihar	2
4	Chhattisgarh	9
5	Gujarat	30
6	Haryana	20
7	Himachal Pradesh	17
8	Jharkhand	7
9	Karnataka	14
10	Meghalaya	8
11	Mizoram	1
12	Madhya Pradesh	24
13	Maharashtra	9
14	Manipur	1
15	Nagaland	3
16	Odisha	4
17	Punjab	15
18	Rajasthan	46
19	Sikkim	5
20	Tripura	1
21	Uttar Pradesh	29
22	Uttarakhand	13
23	West Bengal	9
	Grand Total	279

As far as the universities are concerned it has classified into a state university, private university, and central university. The first two types are normally started by corresponding act passed by the concerned state legislative assembly with later due approval from UGC. While the third one is under the central government Act passed by the parliament. However, it is important to note that, apart from these universities there is another category called 'Deemed to be University' which is granted directly by the UGC under Section 3. Normally the status is offered to them having excellence in higher education, training, and research in the concerned subject. The Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) segment also deals a large number of colleges (40000+) in general and professional stream [19], [21], [22].

Informatics and Emerging Trends

The branch and study of informatics in Indian universities are available only with bio informatics branch. Though India holds about 40000+ HEI and about 800+ universities but only a few have offered this branch. It is important to note that a large number of universities and HEIs in India offering information technology, computer science, computer engineering, computer Applications but the

branch informatics (without any sector-based focus) is still absent except University of Delhi offered an MSc-Informatics program. Though core related branch and area i.e. information science is offered in different universities and institutions and available in around 15 institutions. As this study is mainly concentrated on Private Universities hence the availability of such programs in other HEIs not considered and studied. However, the Table: 2 provide details on private universities offering informatics program.

Table 2. Private Universities and availability of Informatics branches (also domain based)

Sl. No.	Informatics at Private Universities		
	Universities	UG	PG
1	Amity University, Gurgaon	BTech (Bio Informatics)	
2	SRM University, NCR	BTech-(Bio Informatics)	
3	Jaypee University of Information Technology, HR	BTech-(Bio Informatics)	
4	Galgotias University, UP	BTech (H)-CSE (Informatics)	
5	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	BTech (H)-CSE (Informatics)	
6	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	BTech (H) (Health Informatics)	-CSE
7	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	BTech (H) (Geo Informatics)	-CSE
8	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	BTech (H) (Tele Informatics)	-CSE
9	Himalayan University, Arunachal Pradesh		MSc (Geo Informatics)
10	Pragyan International University		MSc (Geo Informatics)
11	Sangam University, Rajasthan		MSc (Geo Informatics)
12	Sikkim Manipal University, Sikkim		PGD in Geo Informatics
13	Amity University, Uttar Pradesh		MTech-Geo Informatics
14	Institute of Trans -Disciplinary Health Sciences and Technology University		Integrated MSc-CS (Health Informatics)
15	Chitkara University, Punjab		MBA (Health IT) with Fortis
16	Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences & Technology, Rajasthan	BSc-Health Informatics	PGD Nursing PGD Health Informatics MSc-Health Informatics
17	Jaipur National University, Rajasthan	BSc-Bio Informatics	MSc-Bio Informatics
18	Mody University of Science and Technology, Rajasthan		PGD in Bio Informatics
19	Shridhar University, Rajasthan		MSc-Bio Informatics
20	Singhania University, Rajasthan		MSc-Bio Informatics
21	Galgotias University, Uttar Pradesh		MSc-Bio Informatics
22	IIFTM University, Uttar Pradesh		MTech- Bio Informatics
23	Maharishi University of Information Technology, Uttar Pradesh		MSc-Bio Informatics
24	The Neotia University, West Bengal		Integrated MSc -Bio Tech & Bio Informatics

Informatics and Bio Sciences: The rising context

As far as these universities are concerned a total 28 programs are offered by informatics related branches. Among these highest number of programs offered by the Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences & Technology (MGUMST), Rajasthan (total 4 programs) while the same number of programs (four) also offered by the University of Petroleum and Energy Studies (UPES), UK. The MGUMST offers only bio information sciences branches viz. BSc-Health Informatics, PGD Nursing, PGD Health Informatics, MSc-Health Informatics. While University of

Petroleum and Energy Studies (UPES), UK, offers a different kind of Informatics areas with a specialization in commonly available BTech-CSE. Few programs on these are-

- BTech (H)-CSE (Informatics)
- BTech (H)-CSE (Health informatics)
- BTech (H)-CSE (Geo informatics)
- BTech (H)-CSE (Tele informatics)

It is important to note that bio informatics is the most popular branches of the informatics field and as far as private universities are concerned a total 12 programs on bio informatics are offered among 28 programs. Details are depicted in Table 2. It is worthy to note that among these universities total 3 (three) are offered BTech program on bio informatics without any concentration (viz. BTech-CSE) and all are located in central India among the remaining programs from 12 only 1 (one) offered BSc program. Total 8 programs are available in Bio informatics branches at post graduate level. Surprisingly except the Neotia University, West Bengal all are offered the bio informatics programs located in central and North India. Moreover, the Neotia University, West Bengal offered an integrated MSc with the integration of both bio informatics and bio technology.

Table 3. Private Universities offers Bio Informatics domain at UG & PG level

Sl. No.	Bio Informatics at Private Universities		
	Universities	UG	PG
1	Amity University, Gurgaon	BTech (Bio Informatics)	
2	SRM University, NCR	BTech-(Bio Informatics)	
3	Jaypee University of Information Technology, HR	BTech-(Bio Informatics)	
4	Jaipur National University, Rajasthan	BSc-Bio Informatics	MSc-Bio Informatics
5	Mody University of Science and Technology, Rajasthan		PGD in Bio Informatics
6	Shridhar University, Rajasthan		MSc-Bio Informatics
7	Singhania University, Rajasthan		MSc-Bio Informatics
8	Galgotias University, Uttar Pradesh		MSc-Bio Informatics
9	IFTM University, Uttar Pradesh		MTech- Bio Informatics
10	Maharishi University of Information Technology, Uttar Pradesh		MSc-Bio Informatics
11	The Neotia University, West Bengal		Integrated MSc-Bio Tech & Bio Informatics

Health informatics is another domain and intersection of health sciences and informatics/information sciences. It is in general applications and integration of information technologies into healthcare management, health systems, health networking etc.

Among the technologies of health informatics (hi) few popular are database technology, networking technology, multimedia technology, web technology etc. Initially, the branch health informatics offered in the deemed universities viz. Manipal University (MAHE), Karnataka,

Amrita University, Tamilnadu etc. Though, surprisingly among the central universities and Institute of National Importance (INI) in India, not a single offer this important and essential branch of Informatics. The table 4 provides a detailed report on Health Informatics programs and branches in India.

Table 4. Private Universities offers Bio Informatics domain at UG & PG level

Sl. No.	Health Informatics at Private Universities		
	Universities	UG	PG
1	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	BTech (H)-CSE (Health Informatics)	
2	Institute of Trans-Disciplinary Health Sciences and Technology University		Integrated MSc-CS (Health Informatics)
3	Chitkara University, Punjab		MBA (Health IT) with Fortis
4	Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences & Technology, Rajasthan	BSc-Health Informatics	PGD Nursing PGD Health Informatics MSc-Health Informatics

Health Informatics as a branch now is available in almost all the degrees except MTech in Indian Universities (also in Private Universities). The University of Petroleum and Energy Studies (UPES), Uttarakhand, offers a flagship new BTech on health informatics specialization in CSE. While BSc, MSc, Post Graduate Diploma all are offered in Rajasthan based Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences & Technology (MGUMST). Here, it is important to note that in CS (computer science) as well Health Informatics is noticeable in this study (while HI is related with information science) at the Institute of Trans-Disciplinary Health Sciences and Technology University with the Degree of Integrated MSc-CS (health informatics).

Suggestion & Future Potentialities

Engineering program around the world is increasing day by day and in India as well Engineering degrees in private universities emerged rapidly in recent past. The table 5 shows the top five states which offer Engineering at bachelor's level.

As far as bio information sciences are concerned it is a worthy move by the private universities in India for the promotion of biological affairs. As far as BSc level is concerned universities can move towards offering the program for the interested learners. Moreover, universities also need to offer MTech programs in these emerging areas of Bio Information Sciences.

Table 5. Rising Private Universities and Engineering Programs

Serial No.	State	Engg. Programs
1	Rajasthan	33
2	Uttar Pradesh	26
3	Madhya Pradesh	20
4	Gujarat	16
5	Haryana/HP	14

Bio Information sciences in respect of health sciences i.e., Health informatics initiation is a significant move of the private universities. Except for MTech all the degrees are available in this field and hence it is better to start following programs for better biological information systems and infrastructure-

- MTech-Health Informatics
- MTech-IT (Health Informatics)
- MTech-CSE (Health Informatics)
- MTech-CSE (Bio Informatics)
- MTech-IT (Bio Informatics)

These programs have been proposed to keep in mind the current status of the private universities and their programs on offer. Moreover in BTech level bio informatics/ Health Informatics both may be offered as a full-fledged degree or specialization in BTech-IT/CSE.

Computer application is another flagship program and areas of current time and thus all these programs and domains of bio information sciences branches may be offered as a specialization in the BCA/MCA program. Industrial collaboration may also undertake in this field for solid utilization of the domain and knowledge seekers.

Conclusion

Information is everywhere and everyone's need. Informatics like other branches gained popularity internationally. Many universities around the world offer informatics programs and degrees. India is little late in this context regarding the initiation of informatics branch. Though it is important to note that, a majority of the branches of informatics is offered by the private universities in India. Interestingly the emerging tele informatics program has also been started in Indian academia. The field of informatics is also started as a specialization of CSE of engineering degree level in Indian Private Universities, which is a significant move. More specializations in bio sciences such as eco informatics, nero informatics, dental informatics etc. may be started in future for better information world in bio-spectrum powered by the technologies.

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